

Appendix A - Pre Interview Questionnaire Manifestations of Empathy

This appendix contains the pre-interview questionnaire employed during the interview study to collect the demographic information of the participants.

Indonesian participants are excluded from this study due to ethical requirements. The exclusion of Indonesian participants is due to ethical and regulatory requirements. The Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC) instructed us that all foreign researchers conducting research in Indonesia must obtain an official permit from the Indonesian authorities. In addition to MUHREC ethics approval, researchers are also required to seek local ethics approval from the National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN) before commencing recruitment and data collection in Indonesia. Due to these complexities, we decided to exclude Indonesian participants from our study.

Introduction

INTRODUCTION

This survey is conducted as a part of a PhD project carried out at the HumanISE Lab, Faculty of Information Technology, Monash University, Australia and this project is a part of Prof Grundy's Australian Research Council Laureate Fellowship research investigating the impact of human centric issues on software engineering and end users.

The research is approved by the Human Ethics Committee of Monash University, Australia for five years on (Date). Reference Number: 41060

Further information about this research, including a detailed explanatory statement has been emailed to you.

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You are invited to take part in this study. Please read this Explanatory Statement in full before deciding whether or not to participate in this research. If you would like further information regarding any aspect of this project, you are encouraged to contact the researchers via the email addresses listed above.

PURPOSE

This survey will be used to identify your empathy enablers, barriers to empathy and impact of empathy considering your interactions with software practitioners/ customers. It will be useful to us as Software Engineering Researchers and contribute to the field's knowledge, informing future research directions.

PROCEDURE

You are requested to answer this online survey about your demographics and behaviours. The survey will take around 10-15 minutes to complete. This survey will be instrumental in understanding your context and level of empathy. You will be reimbursed for your participation with a 30 dollar (AUD) online voucher upon the completion of survey and interview.

PERSONAL INFORMATION AND CONFIDENTIALITY

We invite you to participate in this study as you are a software practitioner who interact with the customers during your work or a customer who interact with software practitioners, and you have consent to participate in this online survey by signing a consent form. The contact details collected via this survey will be kept confidential. You can withdraw your participation any time during data collection and your online survey responses will be destroyed if you decide to withdraw. After receiving your online response, the data will be de-identified and can only be re-identified by the investigators and the student researcher.

CONSENT

If you agree to take part in this study, please tick the boxes in the following showing that you

have read this explanatory statement, understand the purpose and method of the study and you will answer the survey.

- I am not an Indonesian participant
- I am 18 years of age or older
- I have read the Explanatory Statement and have understood the nature of the research
- I understand that I am free to withdraw my participation at anytime while taking part in the research
- I agree to answer an online survey
- I understand that the data I provide during this research may be used by the investigators in future research project

Hereby, I certify that all the information above is correct. I understand that by clicking the "I consent" below is giving my consent to participate in this research study and this is equivalent to signing a consent form.

I consent to participate in this survey

Basic Information

Section 01: Basic Information

This section is intended to gather basic information of the participants.

NOTE: We assure details of the participants and all other confidential information shared will be kept confidential. The names and details of the participants will not be specified in any of the publication or report.

What is your Country of residence?

Basic Information

Your Email Address

Your Full Name (First name and Last name)

What is your age?

How would you identify your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Prefer to self-describe as;
- Prefer not to answer

How would you identify your role?

- Software Developer
- Stakeholder (Product Owner, Project Manager, Business Analyst, Requirement Engineer, Tester, UI/UX Engineer, Customer, End user)

Think of your most recent role that involved interactions with other stakeholders, including roles such as Product Owner, Business Analyst, Tester, UI/UX Engineer, User, Customer. These stakeholders either work directly with you, or provide you requirements or provide you feedback. Answer below questions by referring to this specific role.

Think of your most recent role that involved interactions with software developers. You should have either worked directly with developers, or provided

them requirements or provided them feedback. Answer below questions by referring to this specific role.

Country of your residence when you were working on this role?

How many years of experience do you have in working with these stakeholders?

- No Experience
- Less than 1 year
- Between 1-2 years
- Between 3-5 years
- Between 5-10 years
- Between 10-15 years
- Between 15-20 years
- Between 20-30 years
- Between 30-40 years
- Between 40-50 years
- More than 50 years

How many years of experience do you have in working with software developers?

- No Experience
- Less than 1 year
- Between 1-2 years
- Between 3-5 years
- Between 5-10 years
- Between 10-15 years

- Between 15-20 years
- Between 20-30 years
- Between 30-40 years
- Between 40-50 years
- More than 50 years

What is the title/designation of this role?

Career Related Information

Job responsibilities of this role include: **(please select answers to all the items).**

	Always	Very Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Requirements gathering and elicitation with proxy users (e.g. customer representative)	<input type="radio"/>				
Requirements gathering and elicitation with real end-users	<input type="radio"/>				
Designing software (UI/UX)	<input type="radio"/>				
Front-end development/ programming	<input type="radio"/>				
Backend development/programming	<input type="radio"/>				
Testing	<input type="radio"/>				

	Always	Very Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Maintenance and operations	<input type="radio"/>				
Fixing defects	<input type="radio"/>				
User testing	<input type="radio"/>				
Usability testing	<input type="radio"/>				
Conducting user trainings	<input type="radio"/>				
User support services	<input type="radio"/>				
Technical writing/ User documentation	<input type="radio"/>				

If there are additional job responsibilities that you engage in, aside from the ones listed above, please specify them along with their frequency.

Career Related Information

During your role involving interactions with other stakeholders, what types of software development methodologies have you primarily been involved in? **(please select all that apply)**

- Traditional (Waterfall)
- Agile - Kanban
- Agile - Scrum
- Agile - XP
- Other (Please specify)

During your role involving interactions with software developers, what types of software development methodologies have you mainly been involved in? **(please select all that apply)**

- Traditional (Waterfall)
- Agile - Kanban
- Agile - Scrum
- Agile - XP
- Other (Please specify)

In the role where you interacted with other stakeholders, what is the primary domain you have been involved in? **(please select all that apply)**

- Telecommunication
- Healthcare
- Sales and Manufacturing
- Field Service Management
- Insurance
- Finance
- Human Resource Management
- Transport, Travel & Tourism
- Energy

Other (Please specify)

In the role where you interacted with software developers, what is the primary domain you have been involved in? **(please select all that apply)**

- Telecommunication
- Healthcare
- Sales and Manufacturing
- Field Service Management
- Insurance
- Finance
- Human Resource Management
- Transport, Travel & Tourism
- Energy
- Other (Please specify)

What was the nature of the organisation you were affiliated during the role where you interacted with other stakeholders?

- Self-Employed
- Startup (5-10 employees)
- Small (10 -100 employees)
- Medium (100 - 500 employees)
- Large (More than 500 employees)

What was the nature of the organisation you were affiliated during the role where you interacted

with software developers?

- Self-Employed
- Startup (5-10 employees)
- Small (10 -100 employees)
- Medium (100 - 500 employees)
- Large (More than 500 employees)

How many team members were/are part of the team during your role where you interacted with other stakeholders?

- No members
- Less than or equal to 5
- 5 - 10
- 10 -20
- More than 20

How many team members were/are part of the team during your role where you interacted with software developers?

- No members
- Less than or equal to 5
- 5 - 10
- 10 -20
- More than 20

How would you rate your affinity to technology vs people?

- Predominantly Human-Centred (more affinity to people)
- Somewhat Human-Centred

- Somewhat Technology-Centric
- Predominantly Technology-Centric (more affinity to technology)

Relative to your own affinity, how would you rate the affinity of your team towards technology vs people?

- Predominantly Human-Centred (more affinity to people)
- Somewhat Human-Centred
- Somewhat Technology-Centric
- Predominantly Technology-Centric (more affinity to technology)

Empathy Test

People differ in the way they feel in different situations. Below you are presented with a number of characteristics that may or may not apply to you. Read each characteristic and indicate how much you agree or disagree with the item by ticking the appropriate box. Read each item carefully before responding. Answer as honestly as you can. **(please select answers to all the items).**

I sometimes find it difficult to see things from the "other guy's" point of view	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I am usually objective when I watch a film or play, and I don't often get completely caught up in it	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I try to look at everybody's side of a disagreement before I make a decision	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I sometimes try to understand my friends better by imagining how things look from their perspective	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>

When I am upset at someone, I usually try to “put myself in his shoes” for a while	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
Before criticising somebody, I try to imagine how I would feel if I was in their place	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I often get emotionally involved with my friends’ problems	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I am inclined to get nervous when others around me seem to be nervous	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
People I am with have a strong influence on my mood	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
It affects me very much when one of my friends seems upset	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I often get deeply involved with the feelings of a character in a film, play, or novel	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I get very upset when I see someone cry	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I am happy when I am with a cheerful group and sad when the others are glum	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
It worries me when others are worrying and panicky	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I can easily tell if someone else wants to enter a conversation	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I can pick up quickly if someone says one thing but means another	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
It is hard for me to see why some things upset people so much	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I find it easy to put myself in somebody else’s shoes	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>
I am good at predicting how someone will feel	Strongly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Agree <input type="radio"/>	Slightly Disagree <input type="radio"/>	Strongly Disagree <input type="radio"/>

	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am quick to spot when someone in a group is feeling awkward or uncomfortable	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other people tell me I am good at understanding how they are feeling and what they are thinking	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can easily tell if someone else is interested or bored with what I am saying	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Friends talk to me about their problems as they say that I am very understanding	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can sense if I am intruding, even if the other person does not tell me	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can easily work out what another person might want to talk about	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can tell if someone is masking their true emotion	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am good at predicting what someone will do	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can usually appreciate the other person's viewpoint, even if I do not agree with it	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I usually stay emotionally detached when watching a film	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I always try to consider the other fellow's feelings before I do something	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Before I do something I try to consider how my friends will react to it	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Would you prefer to receive your empathy profile via email?

- Yes
- No

Block 7

Would you prefer to receive a 30 dollar (AUD) online voucher as a reimbursement for your time?

- Yes
- No

End of Survey

Please click below Next arrow to submit your responses.

Survey by HumaniSE Lab, Faculty of Information Technology, Monash University, Australia
Contact: hashini.gunatilake@monash.edu | Monash HEC Approval Number: 41060

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